

Influence of Employee Involvement Practices on Employee Performance in Public Universities in Kenya

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance in public universities in Kenya. The specific objective was to find out how employee involvement constructs (employee voice, information sharing, incentives, and delegation) influence employee performance in public universities. Descriptive survey design was used, guided by Social Exchange Theory (SET), and a positivism philosophy. The target population of the study comprised all employees in 30 accredited public universities in Kenya with a total population of 35,502 employees. A sample size of 385 employees was obtained using the statistical formula of Fisher for calculating sample size and respondents chosen using stratified random sampling technique. The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. Descriptive statistics was done by computing the percentages, mean and standard deviation which assisted with the generalization of results. Inferential statistic involved hypotheses testing and testing of relationships between variables using correlations. The study found that there was a significant positive correlation between employee involvement and employee performance with a strong regression coefficient of ($\beta = .809, p < .000$). Employee involvement constructs accounted for 65.5% variation in employee performance. This means that when employee involvement practices are well managed, employee performance is likely to increase. The study concludes that employee involvement significantly influence employee performance and recommends the adoption of employee involvement programs by public universities to enhance performance, growth and competitiveness in both regional and global markets. By implementing these recommendations, public universities can foster a more engaging and productivity work environment, leading to enhanced employee performance and overall institutional success.

Keywords

Employee Involvement, Employee Performance, Public Universities, Kenya

1.0: INTRODUCTION

Employee involvement is defined as the systematic practice of engaging employees in decision-making and problem-solving to enhance their commitment and contributions to organizational goals. Employee involvement practices have emerged as crucial factors in enabling organizational performance. Studies have pointed out the importance of these practices in enhancing employee performance and organizational performance. For example, a study by (Wilkinson, Dundon, Marchington, & Ackers, 2020) suggests that employee involvement and empowerment are key factors in fostering a motivated and productive workforce.

In various global contexts, studies have demonstrated the positive impacts of employee involvement on job satisfaction, productivity, and organizational transformation. For instance, (Gustavo, Diego, Oscar, & Juan, 2019) highlighted that participative decision-making (PDM) significantly enhances job satisfaction among employees in Colombia. Similarly, research by (Bah, Sun, Hange, & Edjoukou, 2024) in Côte d'Ivoire's telecommunications and refinery sectors underscored the efficacy of employee involvement in driving organizational change, especially when combined with humble leadership. These concepts entail the extent to which employees are allowed to partake in decision making processes, thereby influencing their work environment and outcomes.

According to (Bieg & Toland, 2021) employee involvement (generally known as employee participation) plays a key role in enhancing the effectiveness of employee productivity leading to overall organizational performance. Various studies have consistently demonstrated that involvement of employees in decision-making process provides various favorable outcomes for organizations. A case in point is a study by (Williamson, Bayne, & Shay, 2020) which found that involvement of employees in decision-making processes allowed organizations to access a wide range of perspectives and knowledge leading to overall improvement of their performance.

In Sri Lanka, a study by (Ekanayake & Padmasiri, 2019) emphasized the crucial role of employee involvement in boosting employee performance, particularly in the competitive business environment. Using the classic motivation theory, the research examined managerial-level employees in a selected company through a cross-sectional survey of 104 respondents. The analysis, conducted with SPSS and Excel, confirmed a significant positive impact of employee involvement on employee performance, identifying management by objectives as the most influential factor. The study suggested that enhancing employee involvement through targeted practices like management by objectives can lead to improved performance outcomes.

As stated by (Ardiansyah & Surjanti, 2020), improved employee involvement strengthens morale and assist them in managing their workloads more efficiently, ensuring they have time available for their personal activities outside of working hours which leads to higher organizational performance. It was further observed by (Panjaitan, 2018) that the nature of employee involvement and participation does not just include the physical activity requested, but also include the mental and emotional involvement of the employee. A number of studies have established that employee involvement in decision making helps to reduce staff absenteeism, increased individual commitment, improved performance, increased job satisfaction, increased loyalty, raised degree of worth within the organization with in turn leads to improvements in organizational performance (Aliyu, 2019).

According to (Obiekwe, Zeb-Obipi, & Ejo-Orusa, 2019), the success of employee involvement relies heavily on the unwavering support of all parties involved, including both management and the employees. Management's full backing and the development of relevant policies are crucial in creating an environment that fosters employee involvement. Without genuine support from management, these initiatives are unlikely to succeed, as it is their responsibility not only to introduce such programs, but also to sustain them through adequate resources and ongoing monitoring. Similarly, employees must be committed to ensuring the success of these initiatives to realize their benefits. Attempting to involve employees who are unwilling to participate is like trying to water the ground by pouring water on a rock, contends (Obiekwe, Zeb-Obipi, & Ejo-Orusa, 2019), and that such efforts would result in a complete waste of resources and time.

(Armstrong, 2016) highlights that factors influencing employee performance are multifaceted, including motivation, job satisfaction, organizational culture, leadership, employee involvement, work life balance, and employee empowerment practices. It is argued that organizations that foster a culture of employee involvement are characterized by practices such as information sharing, employee voice, recognition, and often witness higher levels of employee performance (Boxall & Purcell, 2016). In addition, effective performance management systems and continuous professional development also play a fundamental role in enhancing employee performance through involvement (Aguinis, 2019).

In the context of public universities in Kenya, there is a growing interest in understanding how employee involvement influences employee performance and organizational performance. Public universities face unique challenges, including bureaucratic inertia, resource constraints which create the need for innovative solutions to improve academic and administrative functions. A number of studies have found that employee involvement can significantly enhance employee performance in educational institutions (Odero & Makori, 2018) and (Magolo et al., 2019).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Employee involvement is the practice of engaging employees in decision-making, sharing relevant information, and involving them in organizational activities to enhance their commitment and overall performance (Mwangi & Waiganjo, 2019). Salessi and Omar (2019) found that employees who have the chance to take part in their organizations' activities tend to perform better because involvement promotes their self-esteem and prestige. These findings are supported by (Butali & Njoroge, 2018) who discovered that employee participation notably impacts employee performance and organizational performance.

Despite the recognized benefits of employee involvement in various organizational settings, public universities in Kenya continue to struggle with issues of employee disengagement, low productivity, and optimal performance. This problem is worsened by hierarchical management structures that often limit the scope of employee participation in decision-making processes. The gap in research presents a significant challenge. Without a clear understanding of the relationship between employee involvement and employee performance, public universities may fail to harness the potential benefits of a participative workforce.

The reviewed literature on employee involvement and performance reveal several gaps pertinent to Kenyan public universities. Studies like Gustavo et al. (2019) and Dundon et al. (2022) highlight the

importance of employee voice and information sharing but lack context-specific insights for Kenyan institutions. Research by (Mambula, Francis, & Zirra, 2021) and (Ezeanolue & Ezeanvim, 2020) underscore the role of incentives and delegation in employee productivity but focuses on non-academic settings. Somwaru (2018) provides valuable insights into unionized higher education environments, yet its applicability to Kenya remains uncertain due to differing cultural and institutional dynamics. Additionally, Magolo et al. (2016) and Odero & Makori (2018) provides evidence of the positive effects of employee involvement on performance in public universities in Uganda and Kenya, respectively. However, these studies do not thoroughly examine the specific indicators of employee involvement such as voice, information sharing, incentives, and delegation, and their direct impacts on employee performance.

Addressing these gaps can enhance an understanding of how employee involvement practices directly impact performance in the unique context of Kenyan public universities.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance in public universities in Kenya.

1.3.1 Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the study was:

H₀₁ Employee involvement does not have significant influence on the employee performance in public universities in Kenya.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1: Theoretical Review

2.1.1: Social Exchange Theory

Reciprocal obligations are the cornerstone of social exchange theory, which advocates that parties in a jointly dependent relationship give and take in a fashion that maximizes their benefits. As suggested by (Blau, 1964), social exchanges may be prompted by an organization's treatment of its employees, anticipating that actions by the organization would be reciprocated accordingly. When organizations send a signal that they value employees' contributions and are willing to seek their interests, employees respond with positive work attitudes and behaviors (Aryee, Budhwar, & Chen, 2002); (Huntington, Hutchison, Eisenberger, & Sowa, 1986).

In order to cope with the changing competitive environment, organizations need to engage people who are capable of being both managers and leaders in the way they influence, mentor and develop others in formal and informal capacities. The practice of employee involvement is adopted based on the assumption that employees would be more committed to decisions if they felt involved (Bodenhausen & Curtis, 2016). This theory provides an important framework for understanding the link between employee involvement and employee performance.

2.2: Empirical Review

Many studies have contributed significant insights into the domain of employee involvement and its impact on job satisfaction and performance.

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Gustavo, Diego, Oscar, and Juan (2019) conducted a study on the impact of employee involvement on job satisfaction among workers in Colombia. Their research indicated a positive association between employee involvement, particularly in decision making processes related to general company aspects, and job satisfaction. This highlights the importance of giving employees a voice in organizational decisions to enhance their engagement and performance.

Dundon, Wilkinson, and Ackers, (2022) explored the integration of traditional forms of employee participation with modern patterns of employee involvement. They emphasized the role of effective information sharing in fostering a conducive work environment. Their findings suggest that clear and consistent communication is crucial for employee engagement and overall organizational performance.

Another study by (Mambula, Francis, & Zirra, 2021) examined the correlation between employee involvement in decision-making and organizational productivity in Nigeria. They found that incentives play a significant role in enhancing employee commitment and creativity. The study recommends promoting employee involvement in decision-making processes as a way to provide intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, thereby boosting productivity.

A study by (Ezeanolue & Ezeanyim, 2020) investigated the impact of employee participation in decision-making on organizational productivity in selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Using a population of 2416 employees, their research revealed that delegation of responsibilities significantly and positively influences organizational productivity. They add that effective delegation not only empowers employees but also promotes a sense of ownership and accountability. The study concluded that employee participation had a positive significant influence on organizational productivity and recommended that employees should be allowed to make contributions in policy development as they play a major role in policy implementation leading to an increase in organizational performance.

Another study by (Somwaru, 2018) examined the enablers and constraints of employee involvement in a unionized Canadian higher education environment. The study identified that intrinsic rewards, supportive management approaches, and small team-based work groups are crucial for promoting employee involvement. Conversely, collective agreements limiting faculty autonomy and top-down communication channels were seen as constraints. These findings underline the multifaceted nature of employee involvement and its critical role in enhancing performance in higher education settings.

Effectiveness of organizational change through employee involvement: evidence from telecommunications and refinery companies in Cote d'Ivoire was carried out by (Bah, Sun, Hange, & Edjoukou, 2024). Their study found that employee involvement, coupled with humble leadership, positively impacts the efficacy of organizational change initiatives. This underscores the importance of inclusive and participatory management practices in achieving successful organizational transformations.

A study by (Magolo, Were, Kapkia, & Okech, Involvement and Employee Performance in Public Universities in Uganda, 2019) investigated the effect of employee involvement on performance in public universities in Uganda. The findings indicated that employee involvement significantly contributes to variations in employee performance, recommending that universities adopt involvement cultures to enhance output and sustain growth of universities to ably compete both locally and globally. Similarly, (Odero & Makori, 2018) found a strongly positive correlation between employee

involvement and the performance of part-time lecturers in Kenyan public universities, highlighting the need for structured involvement programs to boost performance and competitiveness.

2.3: Employee Performance

Armstrong (2016) defines performance as the achievement of specific, measurable objectives, comprising both the outcomes and the methods used to achieve them. Employee performance, on the other hand, refers to how well an employee accomplishes tasks and meets job expectations, contributing to organizational objectives (Kampkötter, 2017). A study by (Thelen, 2021) identified several dimensions of employee performance, such as alignment with organizational goals, management effectiveness, compensation and benefits, communication and opportunities for development and recognition.

Employee performance is crucial not only for the individual employees, but also for the organization as a whole (Mensah, 2015). Employees typically engage in tasks such as production, storage, manufacturing, transportation, marketing, purchasing, distribution, business promotion, finance and accounting, human resources, research, and public relations. When performed properly, these activities have a significant impact on the organization's overall production, sales, profitability, growth, and market position (Maiwada, Aondover, & Nnrks, 2023). According to (Duthler & Dhanesh, 2018), these activities/tasks are integral to human resource management, and their effective execution is crucial for achievement of set targets.

In their review of literature on empowerment practices and organizational performance, (Tamunomiebi & Chika-Anya, 2020) found that employee performance, including accountability, satisfaction, competence, loyalty, and commitment, is vital for fostering a sense of meaning in their work. They add that this is essential for employee effectiveness, success, and productivity – ultimately enhancing organizational performance. Hagos & Shimels (2018) further highlight that the success or failure of an organization hinges on its employees, who integrate other resources such as finance, technology, information, and production systems to secure a competitive advantage. These observations are supported by (Muhammad & Irfan, 2020) who assert that employee performance is a key determinant of an organization's overall success.

2.4: Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a visual diagram that captures the main variables to be studied and the presumed relationships among them (Mwangi, Boinett, Tumwet, & Bowen, 2017). The independent variable of this study was employee involvement while the dependent variable was employee performance as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3.0 METHDOLOGY

This study used descriptive survey design using mixed methods approach, guided by positivism paradigm philosophy. The target population was 35,502 employees of PU (teaching and non-teaching) from which a sample of 385 respondents was picked using the statistical formula of Fisher for calculating sample size. The researcher collected primary data from respondents using questionnaires circulated through Google Doc Platform, interview guide was done through Google meet platform, while secondary data was collected from published materials and journals. The questionnaires were self-administered to various online staff platforms and also via individual emails for those who preferred to be sent the link on email. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were used for data analysis. Pilot testing was done on 10% of the population who were not used in the main study. Reliability was tested using Cronbach alpha while validity was tested using content and construct validity.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study received 80.6% response rate from the distributed questionnaires which was considered excellent according to Cooper and Schindler (2015), who contend that a response rate of 70-80% is very good while responses of over 80% is excellent. Additionally, Wu, Zhao and Fils-Aime (2022) argue that a response rate of 44% in an online investigation in an education related field is acceptable. Therefore the response rate of 80.6% was considered excellent and acceptable for the study.

4.1: Descriptive Statistics on Employee Involvement Practices

The main objective of the study was to establish the influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance in public universities. Several questions were asked to answer this objective. The respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreements/disagreements with the statements regarding influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance. The findings are presented in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Influence of Employee Involvement Practices on Employee Performance

Statements on employee voice, information sharing, incentives and delegation	N	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Not Sure	Mean	Std. Deviation
Staff meetings where one can be heard are a common place in this university	310	24.5	25.2	37.4	6.5	6.5	2.4516	1.12168
I play a part in developing the tool used for my appraisal	310	33.5	27.1	25.8	6.5	7.1	2.2645	1.19371
Employees have the freedom to choose how they accomplish their tasks.	310	22.6	28.4	27.1	8.4	13.5	2.6194	1.29360
Employees have access to data and information necessary for decision-making.	310	19.4	32.3	25.2	4.5	18.7	2.7097	1.34606
I get adequate/regular feedback on how well this university is performing.	310	19.4	32.3	28.4	5.8	14.2	2.6323	1.26194
Employees are well-informed about the organization's mission and vision.	310	9.7	12.3	49	20.6	8.4	3.0581	1.02549
We have incentives such as training/seminars to improve on performance	310	27.7	25.8	30.3	3.9	12.3	2.471	1.27363
We have incentives such as end of year bonuses to help improve on our performance	310	61.3	23.9	7.1	0	7.7	1.6903	1.13530

We have incentives supporting employee welfare services such as bereavement	310	28.4	20	23.9	11	16.8	2.6774	1.42077
I am assigned duties with higher responsibilities and mentored on how to perform them.	310	22.6	35.5	24.5	5.8	11.6	2.4839	1.23254
We have coaching sessions on how to improve our performance to enhance organizational performance	310	34.2	32.3	18.1	1.9	13.5	2.2839	1.32076
The management recognizes and makes good use of my abilities and skills through delegation.	310	31.6	23.9	28.4	3.9	12.3	2.4129	1.30117
Aggregate							2.4796	1.24390

Source: Research data 2023

Overall, this variable generated a mean of 2.4796 and a standard deviation of 1.2439. The mean of 2.4796 shows majority view is disagree with the statements regarding employee involvement practices on employee performance in public universities. The standard deviation indicates that there is some variability in respondent's opinions and the views are not uniform across participants.

The respondents were asked to respond to the following statements on employee voice: Staff meetings where one can be heard are a common place in this university – majority 49.7% disagreed (24.5% SD; 25.2% D), 43.9% agreed (37.4% A; 6.5% SA), while 6.5% were not sure. I play a part in developing the tool used for my appraisal – majority 60.6% disagreed (33.5 SD; 27.1% D), 32.3% agreed (25.8% A; 6.5% SA), while 7.1% were not sure. Employees have the freedom to choose how they accomplish their tasks – majority 51% disagreed (22.6% SD; 28.4% D), 35.5% agreed (27.1 A; 8.4 SA), while 13.5% were not sure. A study by (Mambula, et. al, 2021) revealed that enabling all employees to participate in decision making fosters worker commitment, creativity, and innovation within the organization.

The respondents were asked the following questions on the indicator information sharing: Employees have access to data and information necessary for decision-making - majority 51.7% disagreed (19.4% SD; 32.3% D), 29.7% agreed (25.2% A; 4.5% SA) while 18.7% were not sure. I get adequate/regular feedback on how well this university is performing - majority 51.7% disagreed (19.4% SD; 32.3% D), 34.2% agreed (28.4% A; 5.8% SA) while 14.2% were not sure. Employees are well-informed about the organization's mission and vision - majority 69.6% agreed (49% A; 20.62% SA), 22% disagreed (9.7% SD; 12.3% D) while 8.4% were not sure. A study by (Moazzma, Muhammad, & Muhammad, 2017) established that information sharing accelerates decision making and boosts employee commitment and job satisfaction which has an overall impact on employee performance. That a committed and competent workforce helps organizations to succeed and gain a competitive edge, provided they are involved in both the formulation and implementation of the strategies.

On incentives, the respondents were asked the following questions: We have incentives such as training/seminars to improve on performance - majority 53.5% disagreed (27.7% SD; 25.8% D), 29.7% agreed (30.3% A; 3.9% SA), while 12.3% were not sure. We have incentives such as end of year bonuses to help improve on our performance - majority 85.2% disagreed (61.3% SD; 23.9% D), 34.2% agreed (7.1% A), while 7.7% were not sure. We have incentives supporting employee welfare services such as bereavement - majority 48.4% disagreed (28.4% SD; 20% D), 34.9% agreed (23.9% A; 11% SA), while 16.8% were not sure. A study by (Aswin & Anandan, 2023) suggested that

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creating a supportive work environment with job features, incentives, and recognition, along with a focus on employee well-being, can enhance employee engagement and boost employee performance. That providing rewards to employees can also improve performance.

The respondents were asked the following questions on delegation: I am assigned duties with higher responsibilities and mentored on how to perform them - majority 58.1% disagreed (22.6% SD; 35.5% D), 30.3% agreed (24.5% A; 5.8% SA) while 11.6% were not sure. We have coaching sessions on how to improve our performance to enhance employee performance - majority 66.5% disagreed (34.2% SD; 32.3% D), 20% agreed (18.1% A; 1.9% SA) while 13.5% were not sure. The management recognizes and makes good use of my abilities and skills through delegation. - majority 55.5% disagreed (31.6% SD; 23.9% D), 32.3% agreed (28.4% A; 3.9% SA) while 12.3% were not sure.

These findings could be understood since most decisions in public universities are as a result of directives from National Government through its various agencies. Where the decision is institutionalized, only a few of the employees are involved such as Chairmen of Departments, Deans of Faculties, Directors of Institutes, and Senate. These findings align with (Musyoka, Kegoro, & Njagi, 2024) observation that public universities lacked practices in participative decision making, delegation of responsibilities, employee motivation, and departmental flexibility, raising significant concerns.

4.2: Descriptive Statistics on Employee Performance

This section is concerned with the investigation of employee performance in public universities in Kenya. The findings presented in Table 4.2 below represent the respondent's responses to the questions on indicators of employee performance for that study which were: employee satisfaction, employee commitment and employee loyalty.

Table 4.2: Employee Performance

Statements on employee satisfaction, employee loyalty and employee commitment	N	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Not Sure	Mean	Std. Deviation
I am satisfied with my current compensation and benefits package.	310	41.3	39.4	9	1.9	8.4	1.9677	1.15705
I believe that my compensation reflects my skills and contributions to this university	310	39.4	32.3	11.6	3.2	13.5	2.1935	1.35148
This university provides opportunities for my professional growth	310	25.8	29.7	27.7	9.7	7.1	2.4258	1.17662
I am satisfied with the training and development programs offered by this university	310	27.1	31.6	23.9	5.8	11.6	2.4323	1.26706
I am satisfied with my current job and feel a sense of loyalty to this university.	310	14.8	23.9	33.5	14.8	12.9	2.871	1.21857
I would still chose to work in this university even if other opportunities are available.	310	22.6	15.5	25.2	16.1	20.6	2.9677	1.43204
I would recommend this university to my family/friends as a great place to work	310	12.3	18.7	29.7	21.9	17.4	3.1355	1.25710

I am likely to explore job opportunities outside this university	310	9.7	14.8	27.1	33.5	14.8	3.2903	1.17673
I am likely to continue working at this university for the next 5 years	310	9	13.5	31.6	16.8	29	3.4323	1.28229
I am willing to invest extra effort to help this university achieve its objectives	310	4.5	10.3	48.4	24.5	12.3	3.2968	0.96659
The values of this university aligns with my personal values	310	5.8	16.1	40	16.1	21.9	3.3226	1.15434
This university prioritizes the well-being and growth of employees	310	20	36.1	18.7	7.1	18.1	2.671	1.36109
Aggregate							2.8339	1.2334

Source: Research data 2023

The respondents were asked the following questions in relation to employee satisfaction: I am satisfied with my current compensation and benefits package – majority 41.3% strongly disagreed, 39.4% disagreed, 8.4% were not sure, 9% agreed, while 1.9% strongly agreed. I believe that my compensation reflects my skills and contributions to this university—majority 39.4% strongly disagreed, 32.3% disagreed, 13.5% were not sure, 11.6% agreed, while 3.2% strongly agreed. This university provides opportunities for my professional growth – 29.7% strongly disagreed, 27.7% agreed, 25.8% strongly disagreed, 9.7% strongly agreed, while 7.1% were not sure. I am satisfied with the training and development programs offered by this university – majority 31.6% disagreed, 27.1% strongly disagreed, 23.9% agreed, 11.6% were not sure, while 5.8% strongly agreed.

The respondents were asked the following questions in relation to employee loyalty. I am satisfied with my current job and feel a sense of loyalty to this university – majority 33.5% agreed, 23.9% disagreed, 14.8% strongly disagreed, 14.8% strongly agreed, while 12.9% were not sure. I would still chose to work in this university even if other opportunities are available – majority 25.2% agreed, 22.6% strongly disagreed, 20.6% were not sure, 16.1% strongly agreed, while 15.5% disagreed. I would recommend this university to my family/friends as a great place to work – majority 29.7% agreed, 21.9% strongly agreed, 18.7% disagreed, 17.4% were not sure, while 12.3% strongly disagreed. I am likely to explore job opportunities outside this university – majority 33.5% strongly agreed, 27.1% agreed, 14.8% disagreed, 14.8% were not sure, while 9.7% strongly disagreed. I am likely to continue working at this university for the next 5 years – majority 31.6% agreed, 29% were not sure, 16.8% strongly agreed, 13.5% disagreed, while 9% strongly disagreed. These findings concur with a study by (Muma, Nzulwa, Ombui, & Odhiambo, 2019) also established that University employees are somehow not satisfied with their work, and are undecided whether to quit their current jobs or not. Another study by (Baquero, 2022) found that employees are most likely to leave an organization when they realize that the performance is declining, due to fears of their job security.

On employee commitment, the respondents were asked the following: I am willing to invest extra effort to help this university achieve its objectives – majority 48.4% agreed, 24.5% strongly agreed, 12.3% were not sure, 10.3% disagreed, while 4.5% strongly disagreed. The values of this university aligns with my personal values – majority 40% agreed, 21.9% were not sure, 16.1% disagreed, 16.1% strongly agreed, while 5.8% strongly disagreed. This university prioritizes the well-being and growth of employees – 36.1% disagreed, 20% strongly disagreed, 18.7% disagreed, 18.1% were not sure, while 7.1% strongly agreed. A research by (Muogbo & Jacobs, 2019) found that in situations where

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the needs of the employees are not met, they will not put in their best towards the accomplishment of the organization's development/expansion.

The findings point towards lack of commitment, loyalty and satisfaction which could be affecting employee performance in public universities. A recent study by (Park & Kim, 2023) explored the relationship between employee involvement practices and levels of employee commitment, loyalty, and satisfaction. The study found that higher levels of employee involvement are strongly associated with increased commitment, and overall job satisfaction. Conversely, low levels of employee involvement result in diminished employee engagement and satisfaction, highlighting the critical role of active participation in fostering a positive work environment.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

The study found that there were very strong positive relationships between employee involvement practices and employee performance ($r = 0.809$, $p = .000$).

Tables 4.3 to 4.5 below give the results for the influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance of public universities in Kenya.

Table 4.3: Model Summary for Employee Involvement

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.809 ^a	.655	.654	.37155

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Involvement

Source: Research data 2023

A regression model was run on the indicators of employee involvement. The results show the fitness of the model used in explaining the strength of the relationship between the constructs of employee involvement practices and employee performance. This implies that employee voice, information sharing, incentives and delegation explain 65.5% variation in employee performance. This was supported by the coefficient of determination (also known as R-square) value of 0.655. Thus, based on this coefficient, other factors that were not considered in the study account for 34.5% of the variability in employee performance in public universities in Kenya. According to (Ghozali, 2018) a low R^2 value suggests that the independent variables have a limited capacity to account for the dependent variable's variance. Conversely, an R^2 value close to 1 implies that the independent variables offer nearly complete information required to predict the variation in the dependent variable.

Table 4.4: Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	80.744	1	80.744	584.889	.000 ^b
	Residual	42.520	308	.138		
	Total	123.264	309			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Involvement Practices

Source: Research data 2023

The purpose of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is to show the total amount of variation in a set of data broken down into two types, the amount which can be attributed to specified causes. The ANOVA for regression coefficient in Table 4.4 above revealed ($F = 584.889$; p - value = $.000^b$). This therefore, implied that the regression model statistically and significantly predicts the outcome variable (employee performance) and is a good fit for the data. This is an indication that there is a significant positive relationship between employee involvement, and employee performance in public universities in Kenya. The results also confirm that the indicators (employee voice, information sharing, incentives and delegation) are good predictors of employee performance.

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4.4: Regression Coefficients for Employee Involvement

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	Beta		
	β	Std. Error	Coefficients			
1	(Constant)	.628	.094		6.702	.000
	Employee Involvement	.774	.032	.809	24.184	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research data 2023

The study hypothesized that employee involvement has no significant influence on employee performance of public universities in Kenya. The study findings indicated that there was a positive significant relationship between employee involvement and employee performance ($\beta = .809$, $t = 24.184$, $p < .000$) hence rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. These findings are in tandem with the study by (Odero & Makori, 2018) which established a strong positive correlation between employee involvement and employee performance ($r = 0.665$; $p < 0.01$), with employee involvement accounting for 44.2% of the total variance in part-time lecturers' performance in public universities.

Based on these results, the regression model fitted as: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon_i$ therefore hold true.

The following regression model was postulated; $Y = Y = .628 + 0.774X_2 + 0.094$

5.0 CONCLUSION

The study concludes that employee involvement practices significantly and positively influence employee performance in public universities in Kenya. With a strong regression coefficient ($\beta = .809$, $p < .000$), it is evident that enhancing employee involvement through practices such as employee voice, information sharing, incentives, and delegation, can lead to substantial improvements in employee performance.

The indicators of employee involvement used in the study were found to be crucial in enhancing employee performance. Each of these elements contributes to creating a more inclusive and empowering work environment, which in turn fosters higher levels of motivation, job satisfaction, and productivity, among employees.

The study highlights that employee voice and information sharing are particularly important in enabling employees to feel valued and informed, leading to better decision-making and engagement with their work.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it is recommended that public universities in Kenya prioritize and strengthen employee involvement practices. This can be achieved by implementing structured programs that encourage active employee participation in decision-making, ensuring transparent and frequent information sharing, providing appropriate incentives, and delegating responsibilities effectively. These measures will not only boost employee morale and commitment, but also drive improved performance, contributing to the universities' growth and competitive advantage.

AREAS FOR FURTHER STUDY

Future research could explore the impact of specific employee involvement practices on different dimensions of performance, such as teaching effectiveness, research output, and administrative efficiency. Additionally, studies could investigate the moderating effects of organizational culture, leadership styles, and union presence on the relationship between employee involvement and performance. Comparative studies between public and private universities could also provide deeper insights into how institutional differences affect the effectiveness of employee involvement practices.

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